

Inducing Matrix Sparsity Bias for Improved Dynamic Identification of Parallel Kinematic Manipulators using Deep Learning*

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Abstract—Among the many challenges of parallel kinematic manipulators, achieving high-speed and accurate control remains crucial. Estimating their dynamic properties is essential for designing precise and efficient control schemes. Conventional methods for dynamic model identification have been effective, though deep learning approaches have historically faced limitations due to data inefficiencies. However, recent advancements in physics-informed neural networks (PINNs) offer a way to improve both control and the extraction of interpretable physical properties from these robots. In this work, we propose and validate a PINN-based dynamic model for a Delta parallel robot, specifically the ABB IRB 360-6/1600. Our approach incorporates known physical properties, such as mass matrix sparsity, to improve accuracy and computational efficiency in dynamic model identification. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study applying PINNs to model parallel robots. The method is validated experimentally, and its performance is compared to a validated identification technique for physically consistent identification, demonstrating the effectiveness of this approach for real-world applications in parallel robots.

I. INTRODUCTION

Parallel kinematic manipulators (PKMs) are designed to have higher accuracy and accelerations compared to their serial counterparts [1]. However, due to disadvantages such as the reduced workspace and singularities, PKMs are applied mostly on industrial fast pick and place tasks, haptic interfaces and pilot simulations [1], [2]. Nonetheless, the fact that they excel in tasks where highly accurate and efficient control systems are required, the determination of the dynamic properties of the manipulator is of paramount importance for model-based controlling such robots [3].

PKM dynamic identification is conventionally carried out using methods similar to those employed for serial manipulators, specifically through the inverse dynamics identification model (IDIM) and solving the base parameter vector via the least squares (LS) method [4], [5]. However, due to the closed-loop nature of PKMs, deriving the IDIM is more complex. The equation of motion (EOM) is computed by virtually opening the loops in the structure, after which the closure constraints are applied [3], [4]. Once this process is

complete, the steps align with those used for serial manipulators. Nonetheless, the LS method often yields physically inconsistent parameters, which renders it unsuitable for use in dynamic simulators that require the inversion of the mass matrix [3]. This limitation also affects other model-based controllers, such as Computed Torque Controllers (CTC) and Passivity-Based Controllers (PBC), which rely on physically consistent models [6], [7]. As a result, the conventional approach is mainly applicable to feed-forward model-based controllers rather than dynamic simulation or advanced control methods. In order to have a physically consistent dynamic identification, the identified mass must be positive, the inertia matrix positive definite, and the moments of inertia in compliance with triangle inequalities, with friction parameters requiring positive values. Various solutions to this issue have been proposed, and recent approaches have successfully produced fully physically consistent parameters [8]–[10].

The methods for identifying physically consistent parameters typically rely on optimization techniques. Traversaro *et al.* proposed a method to ensure full physical consistency of rigid body inertial parameters through nonlinear parametrization and optimization on manifolds [10]. Similarly, Wensing *et al.* introduced Linear Matrix Inequalities (LMIs) to characterize the physical consistency of rigid-body inertial parameters by assessing plausibility through statistical moments and proposed LMI constraints for density realizability on an ellipsoid, assumed to represent the rigid body [9]. However, these optimization techniques have been validated only in serial manipulators. The first method for achieving physically consistent PKMs dynamic identification was presented in [8], where a transformation of the inertia and friction parameters based on [11] is applied, followed by the determination of the full parameter set through an optimization process that includes a regularization term.

Less conventional techniques involving data-driven approaches, such as machine learning (ML), have seen limited application in PKMs model identification and control literature [12]–[14]. Typical ML techniques, which often rely on deep learning (DL) architectures, excel in torque prediction but lack physical interpretability [15], making them unsuitable for model-based controllers like CTC or PBC. Nonetheless, by integrating physics-based principles into DL architectures or introducing bias, the performance of ML algorithms can be enhanced. Physics-informed Neural Networks (PINNs) such as Deep Lagrangian Networks (DeLaN), have demonstrated that it is possible to achieve physically plausible dynamic identification using ML by

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incorporating concepts like energy conservation and friction models [16], [17]. Furthermore, DeLaN+NSCF, has shown that more complex friction models, such as non-symmetrical Coulomb friction (NSCF), along with the inertia of motor drives, can be identified in a 6-degree-of-freedom serial manipulator [18]. While promising, these methods have yet to be fully realized for PKMs.

This paper advances PKMs dynamics identification by introducing a data-driven technique based on PINNs. The core contribution is the validation of the first white-box, data-driven methodology for PKMs that ensures the estimation of a positive definite inertia matrix, positive mass, and positive friction coefficients, grounded in Lagrangian mechanics. Additionally, we leverage the sparsity of the mass matrix [19] as an induced bias to efficiently compute the mass matrix of the EOM. We compare the performance of our method, which incorporates sparsity, with an approach that does not consider sparsity and a baseline method for physically consistent dynamic identification of PKMs. The results, validates our methodology while integrating well-established techniques for efficient dynamics computations into deep learning-based dynamics identification of PKMs.

This paper is comprised of five sections. Section II outlines the physically consistent dynamic model identification formulation use for optimal and DeLaN methodologies. Section III details the methodology, encompassing the proposed DeLaN architecture and the generation of optimal training and testing persistent excitation trajectories. Section IV covers the experimental testing on our rig and the resulting methodology outcomes. Lastly, Section V encompasses the discussion, conclusions, and future work suggestions.

II. DYNAMICS FORMULATION

The foundation for the physically consistent methods of robotic dynamic identification employed in this paper is rooted in Lagrangian formalism. This method assumes that the EOM of any mechanical system can be described using generalized coordinates through the Euler-Lagrange equation:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{\mathbf{q}}} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \mathbf{q}} \quad (1)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ represents the vector of generalized forces applied to the system, while \mathbf{q} is the vector of generalized coordinates, which simplifies to joint coordinates for rigid robots. The vector $\dot{\mathbf{q}}$ corresponds to the generalized velocities, and \mathcal{L} , the *Lagrangian*, is defined as the difference between the kinetic energy (E) and potential energy (U). Alternatively, the kinetic energy can be expressed as function of the generalized inertia matrix (M_j) and the Jacobian matrix (${}^j J_j$) of the j -th body, or in terms of the inertia matrix of the system.

$$E = \frac{\dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \mathbf{M}(\mathbf{q}) \dot{\mathbf{q}}}{2} = \frac{\dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \sum_j \left({}^j J_j^T(\mathbf{q}) M_j {}^j J_j(\mathbf{q}) \right) \dot{\mathbf{q}}}{2} \quad (2)$$

In contrast, the potential energy can be described by using the gravitational acceleration vector, the transformation matrix

from the base frame to the j -th body frame, and the vector representing the first moment of inertia and the mass of the j -th body. Thus, the total potential energy is the sum of the potential energies of each j -th body in the base frame:

$$U = \sum_j U_j = - \left[{}^0 \mathbf{g}^T \quad 0 \right] \sum_j \left({}^0 \mathbf{T}_j(\mathbf{q}) \begin{bmatrix} {}^j \mathbf{m} \mathbf{s}_j \\ m_j \end{bmatrix} \right) \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{g}^T is the transposed gravitational acceleration vector, and $\mathbf{m} \mathbf{s}_j$ and m_j represent the first moment of inertia vector and the mass of the j -th body, respectively.

In the general dynamic formulation for PKMs, the vector of generalized coordinates \mathbf{q} consists of both actuated joints \mathbf{q}_a and passive joints \mathbf{q}_d . These joint variables are interconnected through the kinematic loop constraint of the PKM, which can be resolved via the forward kinematic model. Thus,

$$\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{q}_a, \mathbf{q}_d) = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q}_a, \mathbf{q}_d) \dot{\mathbf{q}}_a + \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{q}_a, \mathbf{q}_d) \dot{\mathbf{q}}_d = 0 \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{A} = \partial \mathbf{h} / \partial \mathbf{q}_d$ and $\mathbf{B} = \partial \mathbf{h} / \partial \mathbf{q}_a$ are matrices dependent on both \mathbf{q}_a and \mathbf{q}_d . By incorporating the Lagrangian formalism using the expressions for potential and kinetic energy, and considering $\mathbf{q} = [\mathbf{q}_a, \mathbf{q}_d]^T$, along with the Lagrange multipliers $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$, we derive:

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\tau} + \mathbf{B}^T \boldsymbol{\lambda} &= \boldsymbol{\tau}_a = \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{\mathbf{q}}_a} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \mathbf{q}_a} \\ \mathbf{A}^T \boldsymbol{\lambda} &= \boldsymbol{\tau}_d = \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{\mathbf{q}}_d} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \mathbf{q}_d} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Assuming \mathbf{A} is square and full rank, solving the loop constraint yields $\dot{\mathbf{q}}_d = -\mathbf{A}^{-T} \mathbf{B} \dot{\mathbf{q}}_a = \mathcal{J} \dot{\mathbf{q}}_a$, where \mathcal{J} is the Jacobian matrix mapping $\dot{\mathbf{q}}_d$ to $\dot{\mathbf{q}}_a$. By solving for $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$ in the previous equations gives the EOM under loop constraints as $\boldsymbol{\tau} = \boldsymbol{\tau}_a + \mathcal{J}^T \boldsymbol{\tau}_d$. For PKMs with analytically solvable forward kinematics, the EOM can be simplified to depend solely on the actuated joints \mathbf{q}_a . Therefore for simplicity, we will consider \mathbf{q} as \mathbf{q}_a , hence:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = \mathbf{M}(\mathbf{q}) \ddot{\mathbf{q}} + \dot{\mathbf{M}}(\mathbf{q}) \dot{\mathbf{q}} - \frac{\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{q}} (\dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \mathbf{M}(\mathbf{q}) \dot{\mathbf{q}}) \right)^T}{2} + \mathbf{G}(\mathbf{q}) \quad (7)$$

which models the EOM as a second-order differential equation. However, in the case of non-conservative forces such as friction, motor inertia, or external wrenches are present, and these can be expressed as generalized forces [16] (*i.e.*, they can be formulated in terms of generalized coordinates), they can be added to the left-hand side of eq. (7). Thus, eq. (7) is commonly represented in the following form:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = \mathbf{M}(\mathbf{q}) \ddot{\mathbf{q}} + \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}}) \dot{\mathbf{q}} + \mathbf{G}(\mathbf{q}) + \boldsymbol{\tau}_f + \boldsymbol{\tau}_{ext} \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{M}(\mathbf{q})$ is the inertia matrix, $\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}})$ accounts for Coriolis and centrifugal effects, $\mathbf{G}(\mathbf{q})$ represents gravitational effects, $\boldsymbol{\tau}_f$ is the friction force, and $\boldsymbol{\tau}_{ext}$ denotes external torques.

The total friction force is usually a combination of viscous and Coulomb friction effects, expressed as $\boldsymbol{\tau}_f = \boldsymbol{\tau}_v + \boldsymbol{\tau}_c$ [20]:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_f = \text{diag}(\mathbf{F}_v) \dot{\mathbf{q}} + \text{diag}(\mathbf{F}_c) \text{sign}(\dot{\mathbf{q}}) \quad (9)$$

where F_v and F_c represent the viscous and Coulomb friction parameters, respectively. In this study, the effects of external torques resulting from external wrenches were not considered.

Conventional robotic system identification methods considers the fact that there is a set of parameters named *standard parameters* that holds a linear relation with the kinetic and potential energy. The vector of *standard dynamic parameters* is defined as $\chi_j^T = [\Theta_j, I_j, \Phi_j]$, where Θ_j are the inertial parameters associated to the j -th body axial moments and cross-moments of inertia, the first moment of inertia and the mass $[xx_j, xy_j, xz_j, yy_j, yz_j, zz_j, mx_j, my_j, mz_j, m_j]$; I_j are the motor parameters $[Ia]$; and Φ_j are the friction parameters $[Fv_j, Fc_j]$.

Hence, by developing eq. (1) and by taking into account the linear relations of the dynamic parameters with the energy equations, the regressor matrix $\mathbf{W}(\mathbf{q}_a, \dot{\mathbf{q}}_a, \ddot{\mathbf{q}}_a)$ is derived which relates the input efforts $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ to the dynamic parameters $\boldsymbol{\tau} = \mathbf{W}(\mathbf{q}_a, \dot{\mathbf{q}}_a, \ddot{\mathbf{q}}_a)\boldsymbol{\chi}_{st}$. Therefore, these dynamic parameters can be determined by measuring torques and computing the \mathbf{W} matrix from the estimated robot state. Given that joint torques and joint states are measured at a frequency f_m , the outcome is a vector comprising the measured torque values $\mathbf{Y}_{f_m}(\boldsymbol{\tau})$, a matrix of observations $\mathbf{W}_{f_m}^{st}(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_a, \hat{\dot{\mathbf{q}}}_a, \hat{\ddot{\mathbf{q}}}_a)$ and a vector of errors $\boldsymbol{\rho}_{f_m}$. Subsequently, the acquired data undergo additional processing through filtering and re-sampling procedures, guaranteeing a full-rank observation matrix by adjusting the standard parameters based on the foundational or base parameters. Therefore, obtaining:

$$\mathbf{Y}(\boldsymbol{\tau}) = \mathbf{W}^b(\hat{\mathbf{q}}_a, \hat{\dot{\mathbf{q}}}_a, \hat{\ddot{\mathbf{q}}}_a)\boldsymbol{\chi}_b + \boldsymbol{\rho} \quad (10)$$

Hence, the LS solution of $\boldsymbol{\chi}_b$, yields $\boldsymbol{\chi}_b = \mathbf{W}^+ \mathbf{Y}$

A. Optimal dedicated dynamic identification

The optimal dynamic identification of physically consistent parameters for PKMs consists of identifying inertia and friction parameters in a dynamic system by minimizing an error function. The parameters are represented by vectors of original and transformed values. Then, a persistent excitation trajectory is executed, and samples of positions, velocities, accelerations, and torques are recorded. Consequently, the identification involves finding the parameters that minimize the error between recorded torques and predicted values. Due to the system lack of full rank, regularization is required, by incorporating nominal parameter values to guide the optimization. The objective function balances minimizing the error and maintaining proximity to regularization values, by ensuring physically consistent results. The use of weighting coefficients makes the objective function dimensionless [21], and alternative methods, such as matrix norms, could also be employed for regularization.

B. DeLaN+NSCF

DeLaN+NSCF [18], is a type of PINN built upon the original DeLaN model [16]. DeLaN+NSCF consists of

two deep networks that estimate the system inertia matrix, $\hat{\mathbf{M}}(\mathbf{q}; \boldsymbol{\theta})$, and the potential energy, $\hat{U}(\mathbf{q}; \boldsymbol{\psi})$. Additionally, four linear networks are used to estimate frictional torques using the Non-Symmetrical Coulomb Friction (NSCF) model $\hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_{fc}(\dot{\mathbf{q}}; \mathbf{F}_c^+, \mathbf{F}_c^-)$, viscous friction with the model $\hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_{fv}(\dot{\mathbf{q}}; F_v)$, and motor drive inertia via $\hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_I(\dot{\mathbf{q}}; I_a)$. The inertia matrix $\hat{\mathbf{M}}(\mathbf{q}; \boldsymbol{\theta})$ is structured by using a Cholesky decomposition along with a positive regularization term ϵ , which ensures the matrix remains positive definite [17]:

$$\hat{\mathbf{M}}(\mathbf{q}; \boldsymbol{\theta}) = \hat{\mathbf{L}}(\mathbf{q}; \boldsymbol{\theta})\hat{\mathbf{L}}(\mathbf{q}; \boldsymbol{\theta})^T + \epsilon \mathbf{I} \quad (11)$$

After training the DeLaN+NSCF, the network learns the parameters $\boldsymbol{\Pi}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\psi}, \mathbf{F}_c^+, \mathbf{F}_c^-, F_v, I_a)$ by minimizing the loss function. In this study, an additional prior is introduced in the loss function by incorporating the power, as originally used in DeLaN. Here, the power includes non-conservative forces, specifically frictional torques. The measured power of the robot is $P_m = \dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \boldsymbol{\tau}$, while the estimated power from DeLaN is $P_e = \dot{\mathbf{E}} + \dot{U} + \dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_f$. The power loss function is thus $\ell(P_e(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}}; \boldsymbol{\Pi}), P_m)$.

Moreover, the loss function for the inverse dynamic model considers the error between the DeLaN-predicted torques, $\hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}}; \boldsymbol{\Pi})$, and the measured torques, $\boldsymbol{\tau}$.

Finally, the loss function minimized by the network is:

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\Pi}^* = \arg \min_{\boldsymbol{\Pi}} & \ell(\hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}}; \boldsymbol{\Pi}), \boldsymbol{\tau}) + \ell(P_e(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}}; \boldsymbol{\Pi}), P_m) \\ & + \lambda \Omega(\boldsymbol{\Pi}) \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where $\lambda \Omega(\boldsymbol{\Pi})$ is a regularization term to improve the learning of a unique solution for the Lagrangian.

III. DEPLOYING DELAN+NSCF TO A PKM

A. Kinematics of the PKM

The robot used in this study is the ABB IRB 360-6/1600 delta robot as depicted in Fig. 1a. This PKM features three kinematic closed-loops, each comprising a rigid link and a parallelogram that connect the base to the moving platform. These loops are responsible for the translational movements of the end-effector. Additionally, a UPU (universal-prismatic-universal) link, also known as a telescopic bar, connects the fixed base to the moving platform, thus allowing the control of the end-effector rotational movements. In the PKMs literature, this type of delta robot is commonly referred to as a 3T1R system [2], indicating 3 translations and 1 rotation of the end-effector.

B. Proposed DeLaN considering Matrix Sparsity

In order to identify the dynamic model of a PKM, we draw inspiration from the DeLaN+NSCF approach [18]. Previous work demonstrated that DeLaN+NSCF is effective for identifying physically plausible dynamic parameters in serial manipulators. However, its application to PKMs has not been explored so far until now. Since the Lagrangian formalism applies to any holonomically constrained system, DeLaN+NSCF could be adapted with minimal changes, bypassing the need for complex EOM involving loop closure

Fig. 1: (a) Graphical representation of the ABB IRB 360-6/1600 Delta robot displaying the 3 closed-loops and the telescope bar that connects the base of the robot to its moving platform. (b) Picture representation of the ABB IRB 360-6/1600 Delta robot used in this work.

constraints. Specifically, for a 3T1R PKM, we introduced an additional dynamic prior: the sparsity of the inertia matrix, which arises from its kinematics. Given that the rotational and translational degrees of freedom are decoupled, the inertia matrix has three zeros in its last row and column, respectively ($l_{o,3} = l_{o,4} = l_{o,5} = 0$).

$$\mathbf{M} = \begin{bmatrix} l_{d,0} & l_{o,0} & l_{o,1} & 0 \\ l_{o,0} & l_{d,1} & l_{o,2} & 0 \\ l_{o,1} & l_{o,2} & l_{d,2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & l_{d,3} \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

Thus, in the case of handling the lower diagonal outputs from DeLaN, we simplified by setting the corresponding elements of eq. (13) to zero. This introduces a bias into the PINN, potentially improving the approximation of the physical system and enhancing computational efficiency.

C. Generation of excitation trajectories

The generation of excitation trajectories for a PKM presents challenges due to the nonlinear relationships imposed by loop closure constraints, which define the allowable range of joint coordinates. As a result, generating uniform sampling in joint space becomes difficult. In order to address this complexity, we employ random sampling in the task space, where task space coordinates z are confined to an approximate workspace, and joint variables are derived through inverse kinematics, $\mathbf{q} = f_{IK}(z)$ [8]. The boundary of the task space is approximated by a hemisphere, \mathcal{B} , within the workspace of the robot. Consequently, the task space trajectory $z(t)$, which includes both end-effector translation and rotation around the vertical axis, is expressed as a truncated Fourier series:

$$\mathbf{z}_i = \mathbf{b}_{i,0} + \sum_{k=1}^{n_f} [\mathbf{a}_{i,k} \sin(\omega_0 kt) + \mathbf{b}_{i,k} \cos(\omega_0 kt)] \quad (14)$$

where ω_0 represents the base frequency, and n_f denotes the number of harmonics in the Fourier series. The coefficients for the sine and cosine terms, $\mathbf{a}_{i,k}$ and $\mathbf{b}_{i,k}$, respectively, define the amplitude of the motion.

In order to ensure that the resulting trajectories remain within the hemisphere $\mathcal{B} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, we used the coefficients ($\mathbf{a}_{i,k}$, and $\mathbf{b}_{i,k}$) and scaled them appropriately. These coefficients are randomly generated from a uniform distribution and subsequently normalized or bounded according to the size of the allowable range for the position vector. This process, guarantees that the generated motion $z(t)$ stays within the physical limits of the workspace. As a result, the random excitation trajectories explore the task space effectively while adhering to the allowable constraints. Notably, no explicit collision avoidance constraints are necessary, as the end-effector position is confined within \mathcal{B} , which is sufficient for Delta-like robots.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{While } \mathbf{z}(t) \notin \mathcal{B} \text{ do } & (\mathbf{a}_{i,k}, \mathbf{b}_{i,0}, \mathbf{b}_{i,k}) = 0.95(\mathbf{a}_{i,k}, \mathbf{b}_0, \mathbf{b}_{i,k}) \\ \text{s.t. } & \mathbf{a}_{i,k}, \mathbf{b}_{i,0}, \mathbf{b}_{i,k} \in \mathcal{N}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_0, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}) ; \boldsymbol{\Sigma} \gg 1 \end{aligned}$$

D. Experimental Setup

Our experimental setup consisted of a 4-degrees of freedom parallel ABB IRB 360-6/1600 delta robot depicted in Fig. 1b. The ABB parallel robot is controlled at 2.5kHz by an Automation PC 5PC910.SX02-00 with an Intel Core i7 6820EQ CPU from Bernecker and Reiner Industrial Automation (B&R). For this work, we commanded a set of randomly generated excitation trajectories sampled at 2.5kHz. Upon measurement of joint position \mathbf{q} and motor torques $\boldsymbol{\tau}$, and estimation of joint velocities $\dot{\mathbf{q}}$ and accelerations $\ddot{\mathbf{q}}$, no particular low-pass filter was used. Consequently, dynamic identification was performed using the obtained raw data.

DeLaN+NSCF was trained on an NVIDIA RTX3090 GPU installed on a Ubuntu PC.

IV. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

A. Experimental tests

The experimental tests presented in this study involved comparing the performance of three approaches: optimal dynamic parameter identification [8] (referred to as the baseline), the DeLaN+NSCF method without matrix sparsity, and the DeLaN+NSCF method incorporating matrix sparsity. For the DeLaN+NSCF methods, we generated a set of 63 random excitation trajectories, and sampled at 2.5 kHz as required by the automation PC. The dataset was then split into a training set of 48 trajectories and a validation set of 15 trajectories. Both DeLaN+NSCF models were trained with attention to both training and validation loss to prevent overfitting. After successful training, the focus shifted to validating the proposed DeLaN+NSCF model with induced sparsity. This validation was conducted by comparing inverse dynamic model predictions including torque decomposition, mass matrix entries, and mean square error performance.

B. Results

1) *Inverse Dynamic Model estimation*: Fig. 2 presents a graphical comparison of the torque predictions and the way they are composed from the different methods applied to one of the validation trajectories. By observing column one, all three approaches appear to accurately predict the torques

Fig. 2: Graphic representation of the torque decomposition comparison of the proposed DeLaN+NSCF considering sparsity (in red), the DeLaN+NSCF not considering sparsity (in yellow), and the optimal identification baseline [8] (in blue). Column one, represents the torque predictions of the whole EOM in eq. (8). Furthermore, columns two to five, presents the results of each of the component of the EOM: Inertial, Coriolis and centrifugal effects, gravitational and frictional torques, respectively.

from the inverse dynamic models overall. However, in areas with higher torque levels, such as in joints 3 and 4 around $t = 8s$, the baseline method tends to predict higher torques for joint 3 and lower for joint 4. In contrast, our method with induced sparsity demonstrates a better fit, particularly for joint 4, where both the baseline and our method without sparsity perform less effectively. Additionally, in regions with lower torques, such as joint 1 at $t = 8s$ and joint 3 at $t = 3.5s$, our methods provide more accurate torque estimates compared to the baseline. Additionally, by assessing the torque decomposition, it is evident that our method with induced sparsity approximates well to the baseline method in estimation of the inertial torque, gravity loads and friction forces, while Coriolis and centrifugal effects presents the most discrepancies. Nonetheless, the dissimilarity observed in the decomposed torque estimations of the DeLaN+NSCF model without induced sparsity are significant. Therefore, highlighting the importance of the induced bias to the DeLaN+NSCF for achieving good approximations of the model of the PKM.

2) *Mass Matrix estimation*: in order to assess the accuracy of the mass matrix identification and the impact of the induced sparsity, Fig. 3 displays a comparison of the mass matrix entries for one of the validation trajectories. While all entries are positive definite, the mass matrix produced by

the DeLaN+NSCF model without induced sparsity differs from both the baseline and the DeLaN+NSCF with sparsity. Although the model successfully captured the sparsity of the mass matrix, the resulting behavior differs. This discrepancy, is particularly evident in the first column and row, where the learned model does not replicate a similar entry, potentially indicating that it learned a different manipulator model that still produced comparable torque predictions. It is important to note that no loop constraints were applied in the PKM identification process. Thus, the DeLaN+NSCF architecture may have selected a configuration that adheres to the Lagrangian formulation and minimized the loss functions. However, the induced mass matrix sparsity appears to have a beneficial effect, embedding knowledge of the loop constraints and resulting in a model that more closely aligns with the baseline.

3) *MSE performance*: finally, in order to evaluate the tracking performance of the three methods, Fig. 4 illustrates the Mean Square Error (MSE) comparison across the 15 validation trajectories. The results show that all three methods maintained an MSE below $5Nm$ for joints 1 to 3, and under $0.5Nm$ for joint 4, indicating similar overall performance. However, our proposed method with induced sparsity consistently outperformed the baseline and the DeLaN+NSCF without sparsity. Specifically, it delivered

Fig. 3: Graphic representation of the mass matrix entries comparison of the proposed DeLaN+NSCF considering sparsity (in red), the DeLaN+NSCF not considering sparsity (in yellow), and the optimal identification baseline [8] (in blue).

Fig. 4: Graphic representation of the comparison on tracking performance of the proposed DeLaN+NSCF considering sparsity (in red), the DeLaN+NSCF not considering sparsity (in yellow), and the optimal identification baseline [8] (in blue). A smaller radius indicates better performances.

the best performance in all 15 trajectories for joint 1, in 11 out of 15 for joint 2, in 7 out of 15 for joint 3, and in 13 out of 15 for joint 4.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a DeLaN+NSCF approach that incorporates mass matrix sparsity for the dynamic model identification of a Delta-like PKM (ABB IRB 360-6/1600). The study validated that DeLaN+NSCF is effective for

identifying the dynamics of a PKM. Our proposed method not only performed similarly to optimal methods that require the full closed-loop form of the EOM, but also achieved comparable accuracy in estimating the mass matrix entries and torque components of the physical robot. Additionally, by introducing the known sparsity of the mass matrix, consequence of the decoupled kinematic structure of the Delta-like PKM, as a bias in the DeLaN+NSCF model, improved both identification accuracy and performance.

A significant advantage of our methodology is that it does not require the closed-loop EOM, making it suitable for a wide range of applications and straightforward to utilize. Furthermore, the fully validated contribution of torques in the EOM, enables the use of model-based controllers, *e.g.* CTC and PBC. The physical consistency of the mass matrix also allows for forward dynamics models, creating a bridge between physical systems and simulations, *e.g.* digital twins.

However, a key challenge in using data-driven methods in contrast to optimal methods, is the need for larger datasets, which can be difficult to gather and process in physical experiments. Our study also revealed that for complex robot architectures like PKMs, additional biases may need to be introduced to further improve the method accuracy and performance.

The success of applying matrix sparsity as an induced bias in DeLaN models for PKMs identification suggests that this approach may be beneficial for branched or tree-structured manipulators. This outcome, opens up more possibilities for future research on applying branch sparsity in PINNs in complex robotics architectures. In upcoming works, we aim to extend our works to other PKMs, and also to explore model-based DL controllers for industrial PKM applications.

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